

METHODOLOGY OF ORGANIZING THE DIAGNOSTIC OF STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE OF GEOMETRY ON THE BASE OF NON-STANDARD TESTS

Bobojonov Azamat Bekpo'latovich

Urganch davlat universiteti “Boshlang'ich ta'lim metodikasi” kafedrası

E-mail: azamat.bobojonov1990@gmail.com

Annotation: This article is dedicated to diagnosing students' geometric knowledge with the help of non-standard tests, highlighting the methods and possibilities of using modern educational technologies in the development of students' geometrical competences.

Keywords: international assessment program, test, non-standardized tests, mathematical literacy, problem tests, closed tests, reading literacy, international requirements.

МЕТОДИКА ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ЗНАНИЙ ГЕОМЕТРИИ СТУДЕНТОВ НА ОСНОВЕ НЕСТАНДАРТНЫХ ТЕСТОВ

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена диагностике геометрических знаний учащихся с помощью нестандартных тестов, освещению методов и возможностей использования современных образовательных технологий в развитии геометрических компетенций учащихся.

Ключевые слова: международная программа оценки, тест, нестандартизированные тесты, математическая грамотность, проблемные тесты, закрытые тесты, читательская грамотность, международные требования.

Enter. It is appropriate to determine the degree of mastering of information and information on a specific subject while monitoring whether students have achieved the learning goal. For this, the student will have to identify the objects on the subject, give them a description, process the data, express his opinion, explain the essence of a certain process, object or event, distinguish the specific features of this process, object or event. These ideas cannot be implemented with standard learning and test tasks, visual and it is recommended to use multiple-choice non-standard tests. These test tasks allow to control and evaluate not only the acquired knowledge of the students, but also the ability to identify the familiar and unique features of the object and its parts. In order to determine, control and evaluate the level of achievement of the educational goal of the students, they are required to summarize the ideas in the educational material, process the main idea, give examples, express their opinion and

defend it. As mentioned above, these levels cannot be determined by means of standard training and test tasks, it is recommended to determine them using non-standard test tasks.

Literature review. Clarify the possibilities of organizing diagnostics of students' geometry knowledge based on non-standard tests.

1. Study of pedagogical diagnostics and its modern methods and tools;
2. To study the state of teaching geometry in primary education;
3. Students' knowledge of geometry based on non-standard tests

Research methodology. The process of teaching the "Geometry" section of the "Theory of Elementary Mathematics Course" in primary education. The methods, tools, collected theoretical information and developed didactic developments can be used to teach geometry in higher education institutions and determine the level of students' geometric knowledge. Functions of control and accounting in the educational process. One of the important components of the educational process is control and accounting. These concepts have their own essence and characteristics. If the teacher organizes control and accounting correctly, the effectiveness of the educational process increases. For this, the teacher should determine the level of mastery of the educational materials of the student.

Supervision (in the educational process) means the process of determining, measuring and evaluating the level of knowledge, skills and competences of the learner. Detection and measurement is also called verification.

Inspection is a component of control, the main didactic task of which is to provide feedback between the teacher and students, to obtain objective information about the mastering of educational material by the pedagogue, and to ensure timely identification of knowledge deficiencies and defects. The first step in the inspection system is to determine the level of knowledge of students in advance. Usually, it is held at the beginning of the academic year in order to determine the level of knowledge acquired by students in the previous academic year. The second stage of knowledge verification is the current verification in the process of mastering each topic. The current examination allows to assess the level of mastery of certain elements specified in the curriculum by students. The main task of this investigation is to study a specific situation taken separately. There are different forms and methods of such verification, which are determined according to the content and complexity of the educational material, the age and preparation of students, the stage and goals of education, and specific pedagogical conditions.

Euler's theorem about polynomials. Properties of convex polynomials

Definition: If the boundary of a convex body M consists of a finite number of convex polygons, it is called a convex polygon. All convex polynomials have the following two properties:

1. The plane P defined by each vertex of the convex polyhedron M has no interior point of M.

2. M belongs to one of the closed half-spaces defined in the plane P defined by each edge of the convex polyhedron. Theorem. Any convex polyhedron consists of the intersection of all half-spaces defined by each of its edges. Regular plurals A polyhedron is called a regular polyhedron if all its sides are congruent regular polygons, and all polygonal angles are also congruent.

Regular polynomial types:

1. A regular tetrahedron, usually called a regular tetrahedron, has 4 vertices, 4 vertices, and 6 edges.

2. A regular octahedron, sometimes called an octahedron, has 8 vertices, 6 vertices, and 12 edges.

3. A regular twenty-sided icosahedron has 20 faces, 12 vertices, and 30 edges.

4. The sides consist of a regular rectangle, a hexahedron (cube). A cube has 6 sides, 8 vertices, and 12 edges.

5. A dodecahedron has 12 sides, 20 vertices, and 30 edges.

Questions and answers:

1. Draw the polynomial with the least number of absences. Say how many edges, how many triangles and how many diagonals it will have.

2. Can a rectangle or a pentagon be a pentagram?

3. One of the sides of a polygon is a hexagon. What is the minimum number of edges of this polynomial?

4. Draw a polyhedron with 8 by 9 edges. After students solve the examples, they take the "Mysterious letters" of each group, read them and explain them.

Diagnosing students' knowledge of geometry with non-standard test assignments. Non-standard tests items used to control and evaluate the level of achievement of students' knowledge learning goals. It is appropriate to determine the degree to which students have mastered information and information on a specific topic while monitoring whether students have achieved the learning goal. For this, the student will have to identify the objects on the subject, give them a description, process the data, express his opinion, explain the essence of a certain process, object or event, highlight the specific features of this process, object or event. These ideas cannot be implemented with a standard educational and test task, it is recommended to use the following non-standard tests with pictures and multiple answers to determine the level of achievement of the educational goal of knowledge.

Determining the level of achievement of the educational goal of applying the acquired theoretical knowledge of students to practice by means of standard educational and test tasks does not give the intended result. Therefore, it is recommended to use the multiple-choice, tabular non-standard test items below.

1. Which of the following statements are correct?

A. If a polygon is cut by a plane that does not pass through the edge, then the object bounded by the cutting plane and the edges of the polygon is called a prism.

B. The sides of a regular tetrahedron consist of regular triangles, with three edges meeting at each end.

C. Polygons consisting of regular polygons with all equal sides are called regular polygons.

Recommendations: The use of multimedia tools (for example, YouTube, Camtasia Studio 6.0.0) in the organization of practical and seminar classes on the module of geometric materials in elementary grades guarantees practical and safe learning.

Books:

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoyev. "We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people." Tashkent-2017. Page 189.

2. Sh.M. Mirziyoyev "We will build a free and prosperous democratic state of Uzbekistan together. T., "Uzbekistan" publishing house. Page 14.

3. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis.-"Uzbekistan". 2018.

4. Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. "In the public education system on measures to organize international studies in the field of education quality assessment" No. 997 08.12.2018. //http://lex.uz/docs/4097073.

5. Press service of the state inspection of quality of education.

6. Yunusova D. Modern technologies of teaching mathematics. Textbook. – T.: Science and technology, 2011. – 200 p.

7. Yunusova D. Innovative activity of the future mathematics teacher training theory and practice. - T.: Science, 2009. - 165 p. 4. Yunusova D.I

8. Lebedev O.E. Kompetentnostny podkhod v obrazovanii /O.E.Lebedev// School technology. - 2004. - No. 5. - S. 5-12

9. Jorayev T. and others. Basics of higher mathematics. Volume 1-2. T. "Uzbekistan". 1995. 199y

10. Farmonov Sh. and others. "Probability theory and mathematical statistics" T. "Turon-Boston". 2012

11. Tojiev SH.I. Solving problems from the basics of higher mathematics. T. "Uzbekistan". 2002

12. Orinboeva L.O. Mathematics. Study guide. T. "Innovation-Intelligence". 2020. 312 p

13. Susanna S. Epp. Discrete Mathematics with Applications, Fourth I dition. Printed in Canada, 2011.